

IDENTIFICATION AND SOCIO-CULTURAL EVALUATION OF INDIGENOUS DRINKS IN SELECTED ECOTOURISM DESTINATIONS HOST COMMUNITIES IN SOUTH-WEST NIGERIA

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ABSTRACT

Indigenous drinks is considered as a major part of gastronomic tourism that offer essential satisfactory first-hand experience to the tourists. Observed dwindling in the consumption of this drinks due to modernization and preference for foreign and caffeinated drinks is a concern that justifies this research. Direct Interview was achieved through snowball sampling of 50 respondents who are mostly female indigenes culturally connected to culinary focuses. Study population was deduced using Taro Yamane formula. Questionnaire data retrieved from 390 and 375 respondents who were randomly selected from Osogbo and Ikgosi communities respectively was analyzed using statistical package for social sciences version 27.0. One-way analysis of variance was used to assess the influence of community respondents' demographic data on their likeness preference for various indigenous drinks. Duncan multiple range test was used to determine the significance among groups at $P < 0.05$. Raffia palm wine, Oil palm wine, Poporo baba, Otika, Shekete, were the indigenous drinks identified within the two host communities. Mean scores from descriptive statistics were used to present respondents likeness preference per identified indigenous drinks within the host communities. A mean score of 4.44 and above indicates positive preference, while mean score of 4.43 and below indicates negative preference. Raffia palm-wine and Oil palm-wine are indigenous drinks identified to be positively preferred among others within the two locations of study. The study recommends that indigenous drinks should be made available and easily accessible within the community with proper hygiene put in place during the production process.

Keywords: Identification, Indigenous-drinks, Preference, Host-communities, Socio-cultural

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INTRODUCTION

African non-alcoholic and alcoholic indigenous beverages are normally made out of local resources; cereals, fresh milk, fruits, and vegetables (Ezeanya-Esiobu et al., 2019). These raw materials are often fermented or brewed, to promote such properties as taste, nutritional value, shelf stability, alcoholic content, appearance, and texture (Siddiqui, 2023). Some groups within the contemporary African societies have come to restrict their consumption to alcohol-free traditional beverages as a result of their religious beliefs.

In the past, though, non-alcoholic drinks were consumed or served to children, pregnant women and the elderly, whereas alcoholic drinks were enjoyed mostly by the male population (FAO, 2012). Alcoholic beverages like palm wine and drinks that are made of millet, maize, sorghum, honey, banana, and cassava have taken a central position in the social life of the region. Despite the fact that alcoholic beverages are produced in different ways across the world and served different purposes, those made in Africa form a significant part of cultural heritage among the producers (Ezeanya-Esiobu et al., 2019; Friday et al., 2022;).

To be more general, fermented drinks have been inseparably associated with the culture and survival of ethnic communities across the entire history of human society since the dawn of human civilization, and the production and consumption of such products is predetermined by the cultures of the region (Ripunjy, 2023). Alcoholic drinks are part of human diet culture, and have a profound historical relationship with human cultures (Jyoti, 2025). The making and drinking of alcoholic beverages enhance the nutritional significance and social relationships for human beings. In Africa, fermented alcoholic beverages are consumed on different occasions, such as marriage, naming, and rain-making ceremonies (Hirbo and Hola, 2025). Several researchers affirmed that despite the rich nutrient constituents of indigenous beverages, carbonated soda drinks are preferably consumed in Nigeria (Abdullahi & Yakubu, 2013; Abdullahi & Abdullahi, 2014; Adepoju & Ojo, 2014, Dada & Awotunde 2017). More so, in recent times there is a growing concern over the dwindling preference for consumption of indigenous drinks, as some of them are likely to be fading off. This justifies the purpose of this research in identifying indigenous drinks, as well as the preference for the drinks in regards to the socio-demographic characteristics of the Ikogosi and Osogbo community respondents.

Palm wine consumption in Africa

Palm wine is a very common traditional alcoholic drink in sub-Saharan Africa, which is made by fermenting the sap tapped of the various species of palm (Ojo & Agboola, 2019; Amadi, 2022). The beverage is mainly derived using the raffia palm (*Raphia hookeri*) and the oil palm (*Elaeis guineensis*), which is thought to have first emerged in the marshland area of West Africa (Onyeukwu et al., 2024). The wine made of the oil palm is called oil palm wine (OPW), and the one made of the raffia palm is called the raffia palm wine (RPW) (Nwankwo, 2019; Onyeukwu et al., 2024). The raffia palm is a perennial species that can thrive

only in tropical rainforests and is hapaxanthic, which means that it flowers and fruits once and dies (Agambi et al., 2017).

One of the largest means of livelihood of rural populations in the palm belt of Nigeria is palm wine tapping and production (Djeni et al., 2020). The drink has a significant socio-economic, medicinal, religious, and nutritional value, which makes it be widely accepted and demanded. Palm wine is nutritionally diversified with sugars, proteins, amino acids, vitamins, and minerals; other components, in turn, are rich in yeast populations that are traditionally assumed to be beneficial to eyes (Augustine et al., 2013; Agambi et al., 2017; Agwuna et al., 2019). It has also been reported that sugars like glucose, fructose, and raffinose are found in different concentrations during fermentation (Uloneme et al., 2014). Palm wine is drunk by both men and women and has been appreciated due to its nutritional value and cultural excellence. Its production and trade generate a lot of income in West Africa, many people, particularly men, are employed, producing approximately 10,000 liters per day, and making monthly per capita earnings between US\$40 and US\$7,014 (Djeni et al., 2020).

METHODOLOGY

The Study Areas

Osun Osogbo grove

The Osun-Osogbo Sacred Grove is a vast cultural landscape of unspoiled woodland near the city of Osogbo in southwest Nigeria. The sacred grove is around 75 hectares of rainforest flora situated along the banks of the Osun River in Osogbo Local Government Area, Osun State, South Western Nigeria. Its geographic coordinates are 70 45' 20" N, 40 33' 8" E (NCMM, 2010).

Ikogosi Warm Spring and Resorts

Ikogosi-Ekiti, a small village in Ekiti State, Western Nigeria, is located between tall, steep-sided, and thickly wooded north-south trending hills about 27.4 km east of Ilesha (Osun State) and about 10.5 km southeast of Effon Alaye (Ekiti State). It is located in Ekiti West Local Government, Ekiti State, Nigeria, roughly north of 70 35'N latitude and somewhat west of 50 00'E longitude (NCMM, 2010).

Reconnaissance Survey

Prior to the start of the study, a reconnaissance survey was conducted at both study sites at different times to familiarize participants with the locations, obtain consent from the community and other relevant stakeholders, and determine the suitability of the research instrument designed for the study.

Pilot Testing

A pilot study was undertaken to validate the questionnaire content, which was consistent with the research aims (Nwokorie & Adeniyi, 2021). The Cronbach's Alpha reliability test was used to validate the results of the pilot consumer testing. Cronbach's Alpha formula is as follows:

$$\alpha = N \cdot \frac{\bar{c}}{\bar{v}} + (N-1) \cdot \bar{c}$$

Where; N = the number of items.

\bar{c} = average covariance between item-pairs

\bar{v} = average variance

Data Collection Instruments, Sample Size Determination, Analysis, and Hypothesis Testing

Data Collection Instruments

This study used both primary and secondary data collection methods. Secondary data was acquired from site management and other approved agencies. Primary data was acquired through organized interviews of 50 respondents who are culturally connected to culinary focuses (Ibnouf, 2012; Oleschuk, 2019; Reddy and Dam, 2020;; Mocănașu, 2020) via snowball sampling (within a 3-kilometer radius of the ecotourism destinations). Questionnaires were distributed to community members to examine their likeness attitude of the indigenous drinks using a 7-point Likert-Likeness scale.

Sample Size Determination for Questionnaires

The study gathered data on the population of each municipality using the National Population Commission's 2023 projections. The sample size for this study was determined using the Taro Yamane formula (Yamane, 1973), with a 95% confidence level.

The calculation formula of Taro Yamane is presented as follows. Where :

$$n = \frac{N}{1 + Ne^2}$$

n = sample size required

N = population size

e = permissible error in the population (5%)

$$\text{Osogbo Sample size (n)} = \frac{N (\text{Population size})}{1 + Ne^2}$$

$$\text{Osogbo (n)} = \frac{796000}{1 + 796000(0.0025)}$$

= 399.8, approximately the sample size is 400

$$\text{Ikogosi Sample size (n)} = \frac{176892}{1 + 176892(0.0025)}$$

Ikogosi (n) = 399.1, approximately the sample size is 399

Questionnaires were administered based on the result of the sample size at both locations. 400 Questionnaires were administered within the Osogbo community, while 399 were administered within the Ikogosi community. Although, 390 and 375 questionnaires (Table 1) were successfully filled by the community members and retrieved for data analysis.

Table 1: Sample size and successfully retrieved questionnaire (survey) population

Location	Estimated Population	Sample Size	Survey Population
Osogbo	796000	400	390
Ikogosi	176892	399	375

Source: Field Survey, 2024

Data Analysis and Result Presentation

The thematic analysis was used to analyze the interview data, and it indicated that different indigenous drinks existed. Data collected in the questionnaires was in quantitative form which was analyzed using SPSS Statistics version 27.0 (IBM, USA). The descriptive statistics was initially used to give a summary of the data and then Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) was done to assess the significant differences between the groups. In particular, the one-way ANOVA was used to determine the impact of the demographic and personal factors on the preferences of the respondents in various indigenous dishes. In cases where a major difference was established, Duncan Multiple Range Test (DMRT) was used to identify certain differences in groups (Olawuyi, 1996).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Thematic Analysis of Osogbo and Ikogosi Community Interviewees

The thematic analysis table 2 shows that drinks often consumed within the Osogbo and Ikogosi communities include Raffia palm wine (100%), and Oil palm wine (80%, 84%), this supports the findings of Mbuagbaw and Noorduyn (2012); Djeni et al. (2020) which asserted that palm wine of diverse sources are the most common indigenous drinks commonly found within African communities. Within the Osogbo community, Otika (Not allowed in the groove), Shekete (Not allowed in the groove), Poporo baba (Not allowed in the groove), Food and drink products derived, from guinea corn and millets are identified as indigenous drinks within the community but tabooed especially in relation with the Osun Osogbo sacred groove. This support the findings of Mmari et al. (2017) which affirms that Interesting traditions and taboos are associated with some indigenous delicacies as was seen in the case of senene consumption in Tanzania.

Table 2: Thematic Analysis of Osogbo and Ikogosi community interviewees

Codes	Themes	Means of Identification	Subjective Response
Identified indigenous Drinks within Osogbo community	Raffia palm wine, Oil palm wine, Otika (Not allowed in the groove), Shekete (Not allowed in the groove), Poporo baba (Not allowed in the groove),	Interview	100% of the interviewees identified Raffia palm wine, while 80% of them identified Oil palm wine as indigenous drinks. 20% of the interviewees identified shekete, poporo baba, and otika as indigenous drinks but which are not allowed within the sacred groove.
Identified indigenous Drinks within Ikogosi community	Indigenous drinks identified include: raffia palm wine, Oil palm wine		100% of the interviewees identified Raffia palm wine, while 84% of them identified Oil palm wine as indigenous drinks.

Source: Field Survey, 2024

Consumer Profile and Characteristics (Socio-demography) of Oshogbo and Ikogosi Communities

The gender, age, marital status, education, and religion of the respondents were discussed in table 3. The finding confirms that female (51.5%, 51.2%) community members were more willing to participate in the research at both Osogbo and Ikogosi communities than their male (48.5%, 48.8%) counterparts respectively. This result is expected because, food and drink sourcing comes natural to most women in Nigeria societies since they are made to prepare and entertain visitors and their families with food and drinks from an early age (Dzeagu-Kudjodji et al., 2019). Culturally, the Nigeria food consumer recognizes the female gender as the cook, especially when it comes to indigenous dishes and drinks. It was notable that the majority of community participants who identified the indigenous drinks were mostly adults within the ages of 30yrs to above 50yrs, while the total number of younger participants (<20yrs- 29yrs) that participated was less in total figure to the adults, thereby supporting the findings of (Dzeagu-Kudjodji et al., 2019; Marsdent, 2000) who opined that elders' knowledge about natural sources of indigenous drinks are resourceful in documentation of the drinks, as well as to revive their usage and feasibility in a contemporary world. Many hospitality industries have adopted the procurement and encouraged consumption of foreign as well as carbonated drinks, neglecting our local drinks (Nyarota et al., 2022).

Respondents at the Osogbo and Ikogosi locations were mostly self-employed (66.4%, 70.7%), Indigenes (59.5%, 68.3%) respectively. The respondents' percentage of the married participants at Osogbo (47.45) and Ikogosi (52.3%) was higher than other categories. This findings is in contrast to the findings of Kara and Mkwizu (2020) whose research view singles as more participatory in tourism consumption activities than married. The respondents at both Osogbo and Ikogosi locations had the highest participation among the tertiary school graduates (59.7%, 58.9% respectively), while the participants who are primary school leavers (9.7%, 24.3% respectively) were lowest. This supports the research findings of Islam and Sim (2021) which attested that level of education influences drink consumption choices. Vladimir *et al.*, (2023) verified via research that travelers (customers) with higher education have a healthier food and drink preference and often fancy indigenous drinks above individuals with simply primary education. The study also shows a good level of participation among all religion groups (Traditionalists, Christians, and Muslims) at Osogbo (37.9%, 38.5%, 23.6% respectively), also at Ikogosi (28.8%, 46.9%, 28.8% respectively). This is in resonance with the statement of Cobbah et al., (2023) that diverse ethnic, religious and regional groups makes a community's population progressively heterogeneous.

Table 3: Consumer profile and characteristics of Osogbo and Ikogosi Communities

Participants characteristics	Oshogbo (n = 390)		Ikogosi (n = 375)	
	Frequency (n)	Percentage	Frequency (n)	Percentage
Socio-demographic variables				
Gender				
Male	189	48.5	183	48.8
Female	201	51.5	192	51.2
Age (years)				
<20 years	25	6.4	27	7.2
20 – 30 years	51	13.1	40	10.7
30 – 40 years	129	33.1	116	30.9
40 – 50 years	101	25.9	108	28.8
>50 years	84	21.5	84	22.4
Occupation				
Civil-servant	131	33.6	109	29.1
Self- employed	259	66.4	265	70.7
Personal Characterization				
Visitor	87	22.3	80	21.3
Indigene	232	59.5	256	68.3
Tourist	71	18.2	39	10.4

Marital Status				
Married	185	47.4	196	52.3
Divorced	55	14.1	50	13.3
Single	87	22.3	70	18.7
Widowed	63	16.2	59	15.7
Level of Education				
Primary	38	9.7	42	11.2
Secondary	119	30.5	112	29.9
Tertiary	233	59.7	221	58.9
Religion				
Muslim	92	23.6	91	24.3
Christian	150	38.5	176	46.9
Traditionalist	148	37.9	108	28.8

n: no of respondents

Source: Field Survey, 2024

Respondents Preferences for Indigenous Drinks in both Ikogosi and Oshogbo Communities

Table 4 and 5 shows the community respondents' preferences for indigenous drinks within both Osogbo and Ikogosi communities. Raffia palm-wine (5.91-4.95 mean score range) and Oil palm-wine (6.02-4.90 mean score range) are the indigenous drinks identified to be common and preferred across the socio-demography of the respondents at the Osogbo and Ikogosi locations of study respectively. This level of preference is identified to be above the respondents preference for other indigenous drinks identified. This is in line with the findings of Mbuagbaw and Noorduyn (2012), who reported that palm wine is the most consumed alcoholic beverage in the West African region. Moreover, palm wine tapping is a very important commercial activity that sustains the lives of rural people in the African region (Djeni et al., 2020).The drinks were well accepted within the community but visibly from the result there was a notable higher acceptance level for raffia palm wine and oil palm wine. This is in line with the results of Oluwole et al. (2023) who noted that fermented palm wine is gaining increasing popularity among the consumers considering that it is composed of natural components and possesses health benefits. The average preference scores in the Osogbo community were between 3.88 and 5.04; 4.79 and 5.41; and 4.57 and 5.14 regarding the preferences of the Osogbo community to the themes of Otika, Shekete and Poporo-baba respectively. The preference mean score for these indigenous drinks aside palm wine is observed to be low. This is in tandem with the findings of Okareh et al. (2022) which revealed that although burukutu (other name for Otika) is an indigenous alcoholic drink preferred above modern bottled alcoholic drink because of its low cost and nutritional benefits, a majority of respondents married with children do not give Burukutu to their

children. This could be due to the resultant side effects and health implications often suffered based on consistent consumption of locally brewed alcoholic drinks. There exists a significant difference between the visitors, indigenes, and tourists within the community and their preference for raffia palm-wine. More so, a significant difference exists between the age and occupation of the respondents and their preference for Otika within the Osogbo community.

Table 4: Mean scores and ANOVA p values (95%) of Osogbo Community Attitude (Preference) towards Local Drinks

Socio-demographic variables	Raffia_palmwine	Oil_palmwine
Gender		
Male	5.66 ^a	5.40 ^a
Female	5.27 ^a	5.18 ^a
Age (years)	p = 0.123	p = 0.096
<20 years	4.59 ^b	4.96 ^b
20 – 30 years	5.30 ^a	6.00 ^a
30 – 40 years	5.49 ^a	5.32 ^{ab}
40 – 50 years	5.56 ^a	5.22 ^b
>50 years	5.63 ^a	5.10 ^b
Occupation	p = 0.106	p = 0.335
Civil-servant	5.26 ^a	5.30 ^a
Self- employed	5.53 ^a	5.28 ^a
Personal Characterization	p = 0.311	p = 0.554
Visitor	5.26 ^{ab}	5.33 ^a
Indigene	5.59 ^a	5.30 ^a
Tourist	4.95 ^b	5.13 ^a
Marital Status		
Married	5.59 ^{ab}	5.29 ^a
Divorced	5.80 ^a	5.68 ^a
Single	5.04 ^b	5.34 ^a
Widowed	5.20 ^{ab}	4.90 ^b
Level of Education		
Primary	5.38 ^a	5.06 ^a
Secondary	5.46 ^a	5.31 ^a
Tertiary	5.64 ^a	5.40 ^a

*a-d means that do not share a superscript is significant (P < 0.05)

Source: Field Survey, 2024

Table 5: Mean scores and ANOVA p values (95%) of Ikogosi community preferences for local drinks

Socio-demographic variables	Raffia wine	Palm- wine	Oil palm- Otika	Shekete	Popora_Baba
Gender					
Male	5.63 ^a	5.71 ^a	4.60 ^a	5.14 ^a	4.68 ^a
Female	5.74 ^a	5.77 ^a	4.46 ^a	5.07 ^a	4.79 ^a
Age (years)			p = 0.006		
<20 years	6.12 ^a	5.64 ^a	3.88 ^c	5.16 ^a	4.68 ^a
20 – 30 years	6.10 ^a	5.82 ^a	5.04 ^a	5.41 ^a	5.14 ^a
30 – 40 years	5.52 ^a	6.02 ^a	4.80 ^{ab}	5.13 ^a	4.58 ^a
40 – 50 years	5.57 ^a	5.61 ^a	4.37 ^{abc}	5.07 ^a	4.70 ^a
>50 years	5.69 ^a	5.46 ^a	4.20 ^{ab}	4.90 ^a	4.79 ^a
Occupation			p = 0.011		
Civil-servant	5.68 ^a	5.97 ^a	4.85 ^a	5.18 ^a	4.67 ^a
Self- employed	5.69 ^a	5.63 ^a	4.37 ^b	5.07 ^a	4.77 ^a
Personal					
Characterization p = 0.004					
Visitor	6.18 ^a	5.82 ^a	4.63 ^a	5.41 ^a	4.94 ^a
Indigene	5.49 ^b	5.69 ^a	4.49 ^a	5.04 ^a	4.69 ^a
Tourist	5.70 ^b	5.83 ^a	4.55 ^a	4.93 ^a	4.63 ^a
Marital Status p = 0.033					
Married	5.62 ^a	6.00 ^a	4.62 ^a	5.25 ^a	4.66 ^a
Divorced	5.91 ^a	5.43 ^b	4.56 ^a	4.75 ^a	4.78 ^a
Single	5.85 ^a	5.52 ^{ab}	4.59 ^a	5.09 ^a	4.83 ^a
Widowed	5.44 ^a	5.57 ^{ab}	4.16 ^a	5.00 ^a	4.79 ^a
Level of Education p = 0.041					
Primary	5.24 ^b	5.45 ^a	4.82 ^a	5.11 ^a	4.92 ^a
Secondary	5.50 ^{ab}	5.56 ^a	4.38 ^a	5.13 ^a	4.69 ^a
Tertiary	5.85 ^a	5.88 ^a	4.56 ^a	5.09 ^a	4.73 ^a
Religion				p = 0.039	
Muslim	5.72 ^a	5.41 ^b	4.43 ^a	4.70 ^b	4.88 ^a
Christian	5.72 ^a	5.95 ^a	4.57 ^a	5.19 ^a	4.81 ^a
Traditionalist	5.63 ^a	5.74 ^{ab}	4.55 ^a	5.27 ^a	4.57 ^a

*a-

^dMean scores that do not share a superscript is significant (P < 0.05)

Source: Field Survey, 2024

CONCLUSION

Indigenous drinks exist in varieties within the two communities of study, based on the research findings. It could also be deduced that social taboos are associated with some of these drinks. All identified drinks are valued within these communities, but palm-wine of Raffia palm and Oil palm sources are preferred above all. Thus, Palm wine should receive greater study attention to promote its production and marketing at both local and worldwide markets because it is a unique beverage that serves a variety of purposes under different conditions. Previous researches have confirmed the usefulness of palm wine as economic goods to satisfy human demands. The study recommends that indigenous drinks should be made available and easily accessible within the community with proper hygiene put in place during the production process.

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